

On Vehicular Model Reduction for Antenna Simulation Using Spherical Wave Expansion

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Abstract—The performance of a vehicular antenna is greatly affected by the vehicle body. Thus, it is imperative to simulate the automotive antenna in its installed state. The large electrical size of the vehicle often necessitates a high requirement on computer resources and a long simulation time. In this regard, a mathematically robust method for vehicular simulation model reduction using the Spherical Wave Expansion (SWE) theory is proposed in this paper. The applicability of the method has been demonstrated with an example consisting of a Hertzian dipole antenna integrated to the side mirror of a car.

Keywords—SWE, antenna placement, V2X, model reduction, vehicular antenna, antenna integration

I. INTRODUCTION

Modern cars have several antennas installed on them for different applications such as vehicle-to-everything (V2X) communication, GPS, LTE/5G communication, FM, AM, DAB etc. In the future, the number of automotive antennas is expected to further increase to incorporate additional safety and infotainment services. However, the radiation pattern of a vehicular antenna is greatly influenced by the body of the car [1]. Therefore, it is necessary to assess the installed antenna performance before its actual integration with the car. This can be undertaken by simulation, especially in the initial stages of the antenna development process. Nevertheless, the full-wave electromagnetic simulation of a car is profoundly demanding in terms of computational resources and simulation time. This is mainly due to the large electrical size of the car, especially at the cm and mm-wave frequency bands. Thus, there is a need for the reduction of the computer-aided design (CAD) model of the car, so that only electromagnetically significant parts are included in the simulation. In this direction, some works have been reported in the literature. In [1-3], the authors have suggested methods for CAD model/mesh reduction based on using coarse meshing, examining the surface currents, and the surface electric field distribution respectively.

An analogous problem exists in the field of the spherical near-field measurement of vehicular antennas, where a large numbers of spatial sampling of near-field is required due to the large electrical size of the vehicle [4]. A solution to this problem has been demonstrated in [4] by utilizing the cut-off property of the Spherical Wave Expansion (SWE) theory. In this paper, the application of this cut-off property for simulation CAD model reduction has been demonstrated. With this method, it is possible to delve further into vehicular CAD model and mesh reduction than implied by [1-3]. Hence, resulting in a significant improvement of simulation speed.

II. BRIEF INTRODUCTION TO THE SWE

The SWE is a mathematical formalism using which the radiated far-field of an antenna can be represented as a summation of spherical waves. It is expressed as [5]:

$$\vec{E}(r, \theta, \varphi) = \frac{k}{\sqrt{\eta}} \sum_{s=1}^2 \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{m=-n}^n Q_{smn} \cdot \vec{F}_{smn}(r, \theta, \varphi) \quad (1)$$

Here $\vec{E}(r, \theta, \varphi)$ represents the outward propagating electric field. The η and k are the wave impedance and wave number, respectively. The Q_{smn} is a complex quantity denoting the expansion coefficient and \vec{F}_{smn} is the normalized spherical wave function. The expression in (1) is an infinite series because, theoretically, $N = \infty$. However, for all practical purposes, it can be reduced to a positive integer value [5]. The lowest value of N , which can be taken is:

$$N = [k \cdot r_o] \quad (2)$$

where r_o is the minimum radius of a hypothetical sphere which can enclose the entire radiating structure under consideration and k is the wave number. In measurement applications, a constant is usually added to the right hand side of the expression in (2), to enhance the accuracy of the spherical wave decomposition [5]. The cumulative modal power (CMP) of the spherical modes is given by [5]:

$$CMP = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{s=1}^2 \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{m=-n}^n |Q_{smn}|^2 \quad (3)$$

Fig. 1. (Top left) Full-scale simple car CAD model, (Top right) Reduced model, (Bottom left) Simulated radiation pattern of the full-scale model, and (Bottom right) Simulated radiation pattern of the reduced model.

III. MODEL REDUCTION USING SWE

In order to apply the SWE theory for model reduction, at first a cut-off value of N , i.e., $N_{\text{cut-off}}$, needs to be defined. This should be done in a way such that the CMP of all the modes within $n = 1$ to $N_{\text{cut-off}}$ is very close to the simulated total radiated power (TRP) of the full-scale model. The corresponding radius of the minimum sphere, r_o , can be obtained from the $N_{\text{cut-off}}$ using (2). Consequently, the portion of the car geometry which is enclosed within this minimum sphere is electromagnetically more significant than the rest. Therefore, this portion can be extracted out as the required reduced model. The choice of $N_{\text{cut-off}}$ is a trade-off between the required level of accuracy of the SWE and simulation complexity (hence, simulation time) reduction. To demonstrate this, results obtained by simulating a Hertzian dipole antenna attached near the side-mirror of a simple car model (as shown in Fig. 1) has been presented in this paper. The simulation has been carried out using Altair FEKO's Multilevel Fast Multipole Method (MLFMM) solver at a frequency of 5.9 GHz, which is within the ITS-G5 frequency band for V2X communication [6]. For simplicity, the TRP is set to 1 Watt in the simulation. The simulated radiation pattern is shown in bottom left of Fig. 1.

Fig.2. (a) Plot of CMP vs N ; (b) Plot of peak gain, average gain and Cosine Similarity (CosSim) vs N . (The green highlighted area denotes a deviation of ± 1 dB from the peak gain of the full-scale car model.)

In the next step, the far-field is expanded using (1), for an increasing order of N , starting with $N = 1$. Corresponding CMP are then calculated using (3). The plot of CMP vs N is shown in Fig. 2(a). From the figure, it can be observed that as N increases, the CMP draws near the TRP of the full-scale model simulation. For the different values of N , corresponding radii of the minimum spheres are calculated using (2). The portions of the car geometry enclosed within these spheres are then extracted and simulated separately. For the sake of brevity, only one such reduced model is shown along with its radiation pattern in Fig. 1, corresponding to $N_{\text{cut-off}} = N = 50$ ($CMP = 0.97$ Watt), and $r_o = 0.41$ m. In the figure, it can be observed that the radiation patterns of the full-scale car model and its reduced counterpart are greatly similar to each other. Thereby, illustrating the feasibility of choosing a low value of N as $N_{\text{cut-off}}$ for the construction of the reduced model. The simulation time and complexity increases with increasing

value of $N_{\text{cut-off}}$, since $r_o \propto N_{\text{cut-off}}$. Nevertheless, the calculated average and peak gains of the different variants of reduced models are plotted in Fig. 2(b). The average gain is computed within $60^\circ \leq \theta \leq 120^\circ$ & $0^\circ \leq \phi \leq 360^\circ$. The chosen range of θ is based on the recommendations of 5GAA for V2X [7]. To assess the similarity of the 3D radiation patterns of the reduced structures with the full-scale model, their cosine similarity (CosSim) have been calculated. The value of CosSim ranges between 0 (no similarity) to 1 (complete similarity) [1]. In the plot of Fig. 2(b), it can be observed that for $N \geq 50$, the CosSim values approach very closely to 1. The average gain values can also be seen to converge smoothly to that of the full-scale model. However, in the plot of peak gain, ripples can be detected. This is mainly due to the recurrence of radiation spikes of insignificantly narrow beamwidth in the far-field pattern. However, for $N \geq 50$, the maximum deviation of peak gain is only 1 dB from the full-scale model.

IV. CONCLUSION

A method for vehicular CAD model reduction for antenna simulation using SWE has been proposed in this paper. The method has been verified against a case involving a Hertzian dipole antenna integrated near the side-mirror of a car. It has been shown that the desired value of $N_{\text{cut-off}}$ for model reduction depends upon the simulation output parameter of interest, because the average gain and CosSim values converge faster than peak gain with increasing value of N . The technique presented in this paper will provide the engineers with a mathematically robust tool for extracting the electromagnetically significant parts of the car for antenna simulation. This will help in reducing the simulation time and required computer resources for antenna placement simulation without compromising the overall credibility of the simulation result.

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